

Flood Forecast Bulletin - Zambia

Issued on 10 March 2026

This bulletin is produced by the IWMI HydroSecure FFEWS system in collaboration with the Water Resources Management Authority (WARMA), providing actionable early warning intelligence for emergency managers, government officials, and humanitarian partners across Zambia.

Supported by

Zambia FFEWS Background

The Flood Forecasting and Early Warning System (FFEWS) for Zambia is built on the Deltares wflow_sBM model, configured as a fully operational, process-aware hydrological workflow. The system integrates calibrated hydrological parameters with spatial datasets — including a digital elevation model (DEM), soil classifications, land use maps, and river network layers — combined with bias-corrected meteorological forcings to support both real-time monitoring and multi-day forecast simulations.

System Capabilities

- Batch execution framework for real-time and forecast runs
- State validation for warm starts ensuring hydrological continuity
- Rainfall accumulation analysis and return-period exceedance assessment
- Automated discharge response evaluation and visualization output

Operational Status

FFEWS Zambia was developed in collaboration with the **Water Resources Management Authority (WARMA)** and formally handed over as an operational system on **23 July 2024**.

Live operational visualization is available via the FEWS platform on the **IWMI HydroSecure Dashboard**:

<https://hydrosecure-demo.iwmi.org/>

📄 **Purpose:** FFEWS Zambia model inputs directly support flood preparedness and mitigation decision-making by national and local authorities.

Hydrograph and Flood Risk Forecast in Zambezi River Basin

Forecast issued on: 10/03/2026

— Real-time discharge
 ■ Normal range (25–75 percentile)
 ■ Minor flood (2–5 year)
 ■ Extreme flood (>20 year)
— Forecasted discharge
 ■ No flood (0–2 year)
 ■ Major flood (5–20 year)

FFEWS Virtual stations for flood forecast and early warning

Station	Current Risk	Forecasted Risk	Details
Upper_Zambezi	Minor flood	Minor flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Kabompo	Extreme flood	Extreme flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Lungue_Bungo	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Luanginga	Minor flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Chobe	Minor flood	Minor flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Barotse	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Kafue	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance
Luangwa	Minor flood	Minor flood	Sustained exceedance
Mupata	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Kariba	Minor flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Upper_Tete	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance
Shire	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Lower_Tete	Minor flood	Minor flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Zambezi_Delta	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance, Rapid rise
Kafe_HookBridge	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance
Machiya_Ferry	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance
Lubungu	Major flood	Major flood	Sustained exceedance
ZAM0802	Minor flood	Minor flood	Sustained exceedance
ZAM0803	Normal	Normal	No/reducing risk

Note:

Current Risk is calculated by observing the behaviour of hydrograph during the past 10 days from the forecasting date.

Forecasted Risk is calculated by analysing the behaviour of hydrograph during the next 10 days beginning from the forecasting date.

Hydrograph behaviour analysed for a station consists of:

- Highest risk category that the hydrograph exceeds in a duration.
- Sustained exceedance over a risk category for at least 3 consecutive days.
- Rapid rising of discharge for at least 3 consecutive days.

- Latest forecast suggests rise in upper stations around Northwestern, Western and Southern provinces.**

- Inflow in Kariba is expected to increase from upstream areas**

- Converging rivers at Lusaka province is expected to raise the water levels**

- Risk of Major flood prevails in next 3 – 10 days across Zambezi**

Rainfall progression in last 10 days made available by GPM v07

Above-normal rainfall recorded

In the past 10 days, weekly rainfall amounts exceeded the 2–5 year return period threshold. This means rainfall was higher than what is usually expected in a typical year.

Rainfall spread across the basin

The heavy rainfall was scattered across different parts of the Zambezi River Basin, not limited to one specific area.

Not an extreme event, but significant

A 2–5 year return period indicates a moderate event in Chobe, Kariba, and scattered in Upper Zambezi and Kafue. While not rare or severe, it was still strong enough to influence river conditions.

Significant Rainfall events were mostly outside Zambia

Most of the significant rainfall risk was out of Zambian premises. However, Kafue had received substantial rainfall March onwards. The risk the flood induced within last 10 days are from Zambezi basin upstream areas.

River levels increased in some areas

Following the rainfall, river discharge increased at a few monitoring locations.

Impacts were localized

The rise in river levels was observed in selected areas, rather than across the entire basin.

Note:

The return period diagram shows:

Rainfall Accumulation

The Return period analysis made on real-time satellite rainfall data in past 10 day before forecasting date helps to understand any rainfall induced current risk in this duration window

Rainfall progression in next 10 days made available by GEFS v02

Moderate upcoming rainfall

The latest GEFS forecast does indicate significantly moderate rainfall events in upper Zambezi basin during the coming 10 days, which can aid the ongoing flow events across the Zambezi Basin.

Scattered rainfall expected in Kafue and Luangwa basins

Kafue and Luangwa basins are expected to receive scattered rainfall in coming week, but not significant to affect the river discharge.

Recent river level rises linked to past rainfall

The increase in discharge observed at a few locations in Northwestern, Western, and Southern provinces are likely a delayed response to the rainfall received in last week with upcoming rainfall next week.

Runoff from upstream areas still moving downstream

In large basins such as the Zambezi, river levels can continue rising temporarily due to upstream inflows, even when new rainfall is limited.

Gradual decline in discharge expected

With no major rainfall forecast, river discharge across most parts of the basin is expected to slowly decrease in the coming second week from now.

Note:

The return period diagram shows:

The **Return period analysis** made on forecast rainfall data in 10 days lead after forecasting date helps to understand any rainfall induced risk in upcoming duration window

Recommendations — Early Action Protocols

 Active Advisory: Major flood risk remains elevated in the Zambezi River Basin for the next 3–10 days. All relevant agencies are urged to activate preparedness measures immediately.

Activate Early Warning Dissemination

Immediately communicate flood risk status to district-level emergency coordinators, community leaders, and at-risk populations in the Zambezi flood plain using all available channels.

Pre-Position Resources & Evacuation Readiness

Pre-position relief supplies, medical resources, and evacuation transport in high-risk districts. Confirm evacuation routes and temporary shelter sites are accessible and operational.

Intensify River Monitoring

Increase monitoring frequency at key FFEWS virtual stations along the Zambezi. Report any rapid discharge rises or threshold breaches to WARMA and the national disaster management authority immediately.

Coordinate with Upstream Basin States

Engage transboundary coordination mechanisms with upstream riparian states. Upstream inflows remain the primary driver of risk within Zambia and require cross-border situational awareness.

For technical queries, data access, or to subscribe to bulletin updates, please reach out to the IWMI HydroSecure team wrd@iwmi.org. Live monitoring is available at <https://hydrosecure-demo.iwmi.org/>. You can also visit AWARE Platform to produce EA protocols for the region of interest at <https://aware.iwmi.org/>. The next bulletin will be issued as conditions evolve or within 48 hours, whichever comes first.